

FORMATION OF EDUCATIONAL COMPETENCE IN PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

Kurbanaliyeva Makharram

1st year student of JDPU

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Abstract. *Ways, measures and methods of formation of educational competence in elementary school students. Definitions of the concept of competence and education. The role of education in primary grades. The formation of educational and educational competence of pedagogues together in primary school students. Theoretical and practical approach to educational competencies and the opinions on this matter are highlighted and conclusions are written.*

Keywords: *education, competence, pedagogue, student, education, family, knowledge, skill, guide, group, cooperation, communicative, support.*

Today, it is necessary to be able to apply the lesson processes in standard and non-standard situations in the education based on the competence approach in elementary school students. The main issue is also focused on educational competence. It is necessary to apply several ways and methods of formation to the students of the class. What is Trabiya itself? Education is a set of measures taken in order to acquire good and necessary characteristics in a person. In the process of education and upbringing of primary school students, various competencies are formed in them. For example, communicative, social, knowledge and several other competencies are formed. Competence is (derived from the Latin word "cometo" which means "I can achieve, I am suitable, I am worthy") - the knowledge and skills people use in everyday life pedagogues use various interactive methods in the organization of lessons and organize educational training, which also forms competence in students. educational competence leads to the formation of active process types in students. For example, educational activities in the spirit of being in a relationship, knowing, learning, ordinary work, respect for educational and national values are formed in students through the pedagogue. It is necessary. Interest in learning, speech, memory, attention and thinking should be formed in primary school students, because the ongoing processes will have a significant impact on the minds of students. Since education and upbringing are inextricably linked, educational competences should be formed in the educational process. The role of educational competence in the educational process is also incomparable. For example, students' respect for science, teacher's explanation of the subject the fact that they listen carefully to the lesson in the process also indicates the first forms of educational competence in them. Our great thinkers also paid special attention to the word "education". The thoughts of our grandfather Abdulla Avloni about education have not lost their value yet.[8]

"Education for us is a matter of either life or death, salvation or destruction, happiness or disaster." A. Avloni [1] Our pedagogues especially took these sentences as slogans. Because it is intended to shape the education of our elementary school students and develop spiritual people for the future. Of course, our pedagogues should approach the lessons in a way that links education and upbringing. The first President also emphasized these words.

As the first President I. Karimov said: "Education cannot be separated from education, and education cannot be separated from education - this is an oriental view, an oriental philosophy of

life." If they try, there will be no progress in education. Therefore, the introduction of educational competence will definitely show its effect. Especially in primary classes, it may be our job to approach them as a group, encourage them to cooperate and work together. Students cannot be formed individually. Competence is aimed at mutual relations among students, widening of the scope of thinking and uniting for a specific purpose. Working together with students, that is, grouping them in activities doing also forms social competence in them.

Competencies formed in students are divided into three levels: basic competencies; general (subject) competencies; private competencies.

Competencies that prepare the ground for the general development of a student's personality are called basic competencies, and competencies that are formed only through the subject of study are called special competencies. It is known that through the educational process, general secondary schools provide students with basic competencies, including communication, ability to work with information, self-development as a person, active social citizenship, general cultural, mathematical literacy, to be aware of science and technology news, and to form competences for use.[3]

One of the most important aspects of educational competence is the establishment of family cooperation. Because there is a role in the educational process that should be carried out with the family. The motivation, support and support of the family is necessary for the child to achieve high goals. It is necessary to avoid only theoretical education and pay attention to the concept of free time of the child. Paying attention to ethics and aesthetics, it is necessary to take him to libraries and museums in order to raise his consciousness. Even applying this process in education, or lessons should be organized as far as possible, away from classrooms, in subject areas.

Reading competency is not running around the lines of the eye. The teacher's work to build reading competency is implemented in the following areas:

1. The formation of reading skills: the ability to read aloud and to oneself, knowledge of the main types of reading (introductory, in-depth, search, viewing). Techniques used: reading syllabic tables, speech workouts, game exercises to develop articulation, visual perception, attention, reading phrases with different semantic intonation, voice power, reading in pairs, working with tongue twisters, etc.

2. Readability. This competence includes the following components: knowledge of the studied works, understanding of literary concepts, their use and understanding; knowledge of books and works from the circle of children's reading offered in educational books for each class. Methods used: keeping readers' diaries, reading notebooks, making their own covers for the works of authors, little books, holding conferences, literary quizzes and festivals, staging works.

3. Ability to work with a book (definition and selection of books by genre, authors, topics, etc.); knowledge of the elements of the book. In work in this area, students work with reference books, dictionaries, and often visit libraries.

4. Skills and skills of actual reader activity, providing perception, interpretation (interpretation) and evaluation of a work of art as the art of a word, that is, according to the laws of this art (at a level accessible to schoolchildren of each year of study). The basis of this competence is versatile work with text.[5]

The creation of educational lessons as a methodical manual creates educational value for students. For example, education in the spirit of love for the place of birth, mutual respect with adults and peers, familiarization with our traditions and values, A new study guide is being

developed in order to nurture, realize their identity, and develop their interest in science and knowledge.

"Education is our future, a matter of life and death. Therefore, we have no right to delay reforms in this area. No matter how complicated it is, we must lay the foundations of school education from today. Because we We have lost a lot of time. If anyone thinks that schools are the work of the Ministry of Public Education, they are completely wrong. Reforms in the field of school education are carried out by ministries and agencies, branch leaders, governors of all levels, scientific organizations, intellectuals, it is necessary and necessary to have the task of the general public. Only then can the expected result be achieved." Sh. Mirziyoyev. [4]

In our research, we analyzed the content of the primary 1-4th grade education subject, using the qualification requirements that determine the level of mastery of the national curriculum and the criteria for evaluating the tasks performed in practical training, the theoretical-practical, scientific-innovative factors of the formation of social-legal competences in students, the integrative methods of the educational process. we clarified on the basis of organization with;

In primary education lessons, a goal-oriented model for improving the mechanism of forming social and legal competences in students is included in the content of consistency, membership and integrative approaches, by introducing interactive methods and non-traditional educational games that ensure the mastery of areas such as creative activities, family activities, public places, and peers. improved; through the interactive method and creative-educational games that guarantee the effectiveness of the goals in primary education classes, we have developed evaluation criteria that determine the level of formation of social and legal competences in students (knowledge of social and legal norms, their implementation, possession of life skills, possession of personal virtues); social and legal competences of students in primary education classes: "presentation" of the acquired knowledge through various forms of education, "choosing a partner", "looking for a friend", "fair of values", "self-criticism", "interactive tour" formed on the basis of the method and creative-educational games, we have developed methodical recommendations that guarantee the positive impact of their active-motivational, creative-inquiry, informative-imaginative components on the creation of an innovative educational environment; [7]

We found out the effectiveness of creating an interactive learning environment that forms the qualities of cooperation, friendship, and legal knowledge in students through the application of integrative, universal, contrastive and variable forms of education in the formation of social and legal competences in students through education classes. [6]

Now, along with theoretical knowledge from education classes and other subjects, it is also necessary to have a practical approach to it. It is necessary for pedagogues not to ignore all the aspects of students and move them towards one goal, that is, prosperity and prosperity. Today's goal is to make the country a prosperous country, to educate persons responsible for maintaining peace.

In conclusion, today's main goal is to form competences in each subject and to reveal and apply its practical aspects. The goal of forming educational competences in primary grades was also the same. Now it remains only for us to act, because wherever there is a way, it is being sought and implemented. Educational competence is a process that is carried out together with the family, the neighborhood, and teachers. This process may slow down and the movement may not grow

significantly in a single education. After all, our children are the pride of our future, our neglect of them, neglect of our era and our rise.

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